

Adaptive Polynomial Approximation for Gravimetric Geoid: A case study using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C Geopotential Development

Tarsisius Aris Sunantyo

Geodetic Department, Faculty of Engineering, Gadjah Mada University.
55000, Indonesia
sunantyo@yahoo.com

Muhamad Iradat Achmad

Electrical Department, Faculty of Engineering, Gadjah Mada University
55000, Indonesia
iradat@ymail.com

Abstract— In this paper, adaptive polynomial approximation method to model the gravimetric geoid is presented. The polynomial approximation model to arrange training of input is for adaptive system. Training data pairs (input and output) were compiled from latitude and longitude data sequences as input training, and an associated geopotential developments datum on each spatial position as output training. By preceded centering of latitude and longitude data, input training formed with following appropriate formula is the polynomial terms. Adaptation process used LMS (least mean square) algorithm in weight updating, and after training session, approximation of desired target was computed by reloading weights into the polynomial model. Model of assessment test used was to validate adaptive model by comparing residual distance of consecutive point from both geopotential developments data and respective adaptive model in geocentric coordinates system. Using geopotential developments data around of Merapi and Merbabu as a case study, the results show that the residual distance between geopotential developments data and respective adaptive model are about 0.0014417 m (in total absolute value with standard deviation is about 4.6906×10^{-5} m) using EGM96 geoid and about 0.0014468 m (in total absolute value with standard deviation is about 4.702×10^{-5} m) using EIGEN-GL04C geoid. Better result could be achieved by adding more training session with smaller gain factor.

Keywords— Adaptive polynomial approximation, gravimetric geoid, geopotential developments, and model assesment.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the fundamental problems in geodesy is to define the shape and size of the earth and its gravity field taking into account its temporal variation. Representation of the shape of the earth can be carried out by several methods; one of them is by geoid. Geoid is an equipotential surface of the earth at mean sea level (Heiskanen and Moritz, 1967). The use of precise geoid related data, in particular its undulation, is widespread in all branches of geodesy and it is often analyzed in other Earth sciences for example in geophysics, oceanography, as well as in civil engineering (Zhicai and Yong-qi, 2002).

Figure 1. Distribution of the Indonesian active volcanoes as the Ring of Fire (Red color is active volcano) (Sunantyo, 2008)

Indonesia, as an archipelago, located partly on the Eurasian plate, which is subducted by the three major plates: the Indo-Australian plate in the south and in the west; the Pacific plate in the East and the Philippine Sea plate in the north. These subduction zones around Indonesia create a ring of volcanoes, which is called “the Ring of Fire” (see Figure 1). A total of 129 active volcanoes exist, and one of them is Merapi as a result of the subductions. Purbawinata *et al.*, (1997) state that the subduction zone is marked by a chain of active and dormant volcanoes which spreads along Sumatra, Java, Bali, Lombok, Sulawesi to the eastern part of Indonesian. North of Merapi volcano is Merbabu volcano which has not had activities more than 200 years. These two volcanoes are located in Yogyakarta city and Central Java (Purbawinata *et al.*, (1997)). These two volcanoes are very often to be used as a research area too many scientists (i.e. geophysicist, geologist, geodesist etc) to have a comprehensive understanding about them. Merapi volcano has been labeled as one of 15 high risk volcanoes by the International Decade of Natural Disaster Reduction program (IDNDR) of UNESCO (Sunantyo, 2008). The integration a multidisciplinary approach (geodesy, geology, geophysics, seismology etc) concerning to understand the structure and volcanic activities of Merapi in more detail is very important and urgent (Zschau *et al.*, 1998). In physical geodesy aspect, gravimetric geoid determination in these two volcanoes using geopotential developments is discussed in this research.

Figure 2. Mechanical block of current adaptive system (Widrow and Stearns, 1985)

II. ADAPTIVE SYSTEM DESIGN

Input training of adaptive system is formed by following associated formula in the polynomial terms. For the 4th order of 2D polynomial (Sunantyo, 2008):

$$h = c_{0,0} + c_{1,0}\lambda + c_{0,1}\varphi + c_{2,0}\lambda^2 + c_{1,1}\lambda\varphi + c_{0,2}\varphi^2 + c_{3,0}\lambda^3 + c_{2,1}\lambda^2\varphi + c_{1,2}\lambda\varphi^2 + c_{0,3}\varphi^3 + c_{4,0}\lambda^4 + c_{3,1}\lambda^3\varphi + c_{2,2}\lambda^2\varphi^2 + c_{1,3}\lambda\varphi^3 + c_{0,4}\varphi^4. \quad (1)$$

where λ , φ and h are longitude, latitude, and geopotential developments respectively, we have 15 terms (including constant term), and 15 parameters. For convenience, we use a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{14} to represent the terms: $\lambda, \varphi, \dots, \varphi^4$ and $w_0, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{14}$ for parameters: $c_{0,0}, c_{1,0}, c_{0,1}, \dots, c_{0,4}$. By preceded centering of latitude ($=\varphi$) and longitude ($=\lambda$) data, input training vector arranged by following appropriate formula in each polynomial terms. For example, the fifth term of k^{th} input training given by

$$a_{4k} = (\lambda_k - \bar{\lambda})(\varphi_k - \bar{\varphi}) \quad (2)$$

The k^{th} output of training data, h_k , is an associated geopotential developments datum on spatial position (λ_k, φ_k) . Mechanical block of current adaptive system shown in Fig. 1 where k is time index, system output f_k denotes an approximation of desired output z_k , and residu ε_k gives the difference between z_k and f_k . Weight updating that has a basic form (*scalar input vector*), gives new weight vector w_{k+1} , and guarantees that adaptation process always parallel to input vector. Output system at time index k is given by

$$f_k = \sum_{i=0}^L w_{ik} a_{ik} \quad (5)$$

and residue estimation

$$\varepsilon_k = z_k - f_k. \quad (4)$$

Both the estimation of *Cost function* $\xi_k = E[\varepsilon_k^2] \cong \varepsilon_k^2$ used in computing instant gradient at the k^{th} steps, $\nabla \varepsilon_k^2$, and gain factor μ , are used in weight updating

$$w_{k+1} = w_k - \mu \nabla(\varepsilon_k^2). \quad (5)$$

Gradient operator $\nabla(\bullet)$ defined as column vector

$$\nabla(\bullet) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial w_{1,k}} & \frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial w_{2,k}} & \dots & \frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial w_{p,k}} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (6)$$

and the i^{th} element of gradient vector is

$$\frac{\partial(\varepsilon_k^2)}{\partial w_{i,k}} = 2\varepsilon_k \frac{\partial \varepsilon_k}{\partial w_{i,k}} \quad (7)$$

By using (4) in (7) and noting that f_k is independent of w_k , we obtain

$$\frac{\partial(\varepsilon_k^2)}{\partial w_{i,k}} = -2\varepsilon_k \frac{\partial f_k}{\partial w_{i,k}} \quad (8)$$

Using (3) in (8), we get

$$\frac{\partial(\varepsilon_k^2)}{\partial w_{i,k}} = -2\varepsilon_k a_{i,k}, \quad (9)$$

and gradient vector become

$$\nabla(\varepsilon_k^2) = -2\varepsilon_k a_k \quad (10)$$

where $a_k = [a_{1,k} \ a_{2,k} \ \dots \ a_{p,k}]^T$ is input vector at time index k . Substituting (10) in (5) we get

$$w_{k+1} = w_k + 2\mu \varepsilon_k a_k. \quad (11)$$

This is referred to the LMS algorithm shown in Fig. 1 as the dash line block. For N training data presentations, we define input matrix

$$A = [a_1 \ a_2 \ \dots \ a_n \ \dots \ a_N]^T \quad (12)$$

where n is data index and using it to estimate gain factor as

$$\mu \cong \frac{0.01}{\text{trace}(E[A^T A])}. \quad (13)$$

where $E[\cdot]$ is expectation operator.

III. MODEL ASSESMENT TEST

Model assessment test was used to validate model. This test compares the distance between two consecutive points given by both geopotential developments data and its adaptive model in geocentric system (Sunantyo, 2008). Both residual distance (in total absolute value) and respective standard deviation are used to asses the modeling capability of adaptive system. For two consecutive points in geodetic system, $(\lambda_i, \varphi_i, h_i)$ and $(\lambda_{i+1}, \varphi_{i+1}, h_{i+1})$, the distance (in meter) is given by

$$d = \sqrt{(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2 + (y_{i+1} - y_i)^2 + (z_{i+1} - z_i)^2} \quad (14)$$

where

$$x = (N' + h) \cos\left(\varphi \frac{\pi}{180}\right) \cos\left(\lambda \frac{\pi}{180}\right),$$

$$y = (N' + h) \cos\left(\varphi \frac{\pi}{180}\right) \sin\left(\lambda \frac{\pi}{180}\right),$$

$$z = (N'(1 - e^2) + h) \sin \varphi,$$

$$N' = \frac{K}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \varphi}},$$

$$K = 6378137,$$

$$e = 8.1819190842622 \times 10^{-2}.$$

Difference between the distance given by gravimetric data d_h and one other given by adaptive model d_f (called residual distance) which defined as

$$\Delta d = |d_z - d_a|, \quad (15)$$

and has a total value

$$\sum_{\Delta d} = \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \Delta d_j, \quad (16)$$

with standard deviation given by

$$\sigma_{\Delta d} = \left(\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} (\Delta d_j - \overline{\Delta d})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (17)$$

represents the closeness of model from its desired target. Denominator $(N-1)$ in (17) referred to the number of elements of residual vector related to the consecutive points selecting.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The two kinds of geopotential developments data are EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C, located in 48 different stations around Merapi and Merbabu volcanoes. The datasets consist of longitude, latitude, and an associated geoid height from both EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C. At the design stage, we use (2) to center both longitude ($= \lambda$) and latitude ($= \varphi$) data, and arrange them following the polynomial terms in (1) to be input training data, while in the output side we use two sets of geopotential developments data to be our desired target. Using (12), it was defined input matrix $A \in \mathcal{R}^{48 \times 15}$ where 48 rows and 15 columns referred to the number of data presentations and the number of weights respectively. Substituting input matrix A in (13), then is got gain factor $\mu = 0.0095$. Now, it was ready to develop an algorithm to handle our modeling task.

Algorithm of gravimetric geoid modeling using adaptive polynomial approximation is explained as follows:

Input: Latitude ($= \varphi$), longitude ($= \lambda$), geopotential developments height ($=h$), gain factor ($=\mu$), and maximum iteration ($=k_{\max}$).

Output: Approximation of h ($=f$).

1. Centering $\varphi, \lambda \in \mathcal{R}^{48}$:

$$\varphi_c = \varphi - \overline{\varphi} \text{ and } \lambda_c = \lambda - \overline{\lambda}.$$

2. Arranging input training based on polynomial terms:

$$a_n \in \mathcal{R}^{15}, n = 1, 2, \dots, 48.$$

3. Training:

$$k=0, w_0=0$$

while $k < k_{\max}$

for $n=1, 2, \dots, 48$

$$f_n = a_n^T w_k$$

$$\varepsilon_n = h_n - f_n$$

$$w_{k+1} = w_k + 2\mu \varepsilon_n a_n$$

end

$k=k+1$

end

4. Computing output vector f :

for $n=1, 2, \dots, 48$,

$$f_n = a_n^T w_{k_{\max}}$$

end

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the first part, distribution of TTG and its corresponding geoid using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C were discussed, while the second part analyzes are contour lines of geoid model and difference between geoid data and its model of EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C. The third part is model of assessment using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C model for the 1D plotting of, data and model in the distance axis, distance of consecutive points and residual distance.

Figure 2. Distribution of TTG and its corresponding geoid using EGM96.

The Figure 2. show that distribution of TTG TTG and its corresponding geoid using EGM96 that all of TTG from Yogyakarta, Muntlan, Surakarta are mostly up (plus) and TTG from Surakarta to Yogyakarta are mostly down (minus).

Figure 3. Distribution of TTG and its corresponding geoid using EIGEN-GL04C

The Figure 3. show that distribution of TTG TTG and its corresponding geoid using EIGEN-GL04C that all of TTG from Yogyakarta, Muntilan, Surakarta are mostly up (plus) and TTG from Surakarta to Yogyakarta are mostly down (minus).

Concerning with the Figures 2 and 3 that the distribution of TTG TTG and its corresponding geoid using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C are very similar (there is no significant difference between them).

Figure 4. Contour lines of gravimetric geoid model and difference between geoid data and its model of EGM96

Figure 5. Contour lines of gravimetric geoid model and difference between geoid data and its model of EIGEN-GL04C

Figures 4 and 5 show that the pattern of contour line of gravimetric geoid height is very similar. It is supposed that there is no significant difference contour line using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C. The geoid height between them are also continue

Figures 6 and 7 show the results of model assesment procedure related to the geoid model contoured in Figure 4 and 5, respectively. In that procedure, distance of consecutive points in cartesian system are calculated from both data and model. Residual distance which are defined as difference distance between data and model are then used to asses the model. From the results, we know that EGM96

model gives smaller both residual distance and its standard deviation than another geoid model, EIGEN GL04C.

Figure 6. Model assesment using EGM96 model for residual distance

Figure 7. Model assesment using EIGEN-GL04C model for residual distance

VI. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this research are summarized as follows:

1. Adaptive polynomial approximation for gravimetric Geoid height using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C Geopotential Development is very similar. It is supposed that there is no significant difference contour line using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C.
2. The gravimetric geoid height using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C are continue.
3. The distribution of TTG TTG and its corresponding gravimetric geoid using EGM96 and EIGEN-GL04C are very similar

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